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MOBILE BANKING ADOPTION AMONG STREET VENDORS IN ISLAMABAD: A UTAUT AND ISM-BASED STUDY

Fida Muhammad Khan

Hibba Zaheer

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Mobile Banking Adoption Among Street Vendors in Islamabad: A UTAUT and ISM-Based Study

Fida Muhammad Khan

Assistant Professor at PIDE School of Policy, Development and Governance at the Pakistan Institute of Development Economics, Islamabad

Hibba Zaheer

Research Scholar at PIDE School of Policy, Development and Governance at the Pakistan Institute of Development Economics, Islamabad

Abstract

This study examines determinants of mobile banking adoption among street hawkers and small vendors in Islamabad, Pakistan, with attention to widely used mobile financial services (e.g., EasyPaisa, JazzCash, Sadapay). Using semi-structured interviews and thematic analysis guided by the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), the study identifies key drivers and constraints shaping adoption and

use. In addition, Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) and MICMAC analysis are applied to map the hierarchical interrelationships among determinants, clarifying leverage points for accelerating adoption in the informal economy. Findings indicate that awareness and social influence serve as foundational drivers, while accessibility and network reliability shape enabling conditions. Trust, perceived ease of use, and perceived business value mediate continued engagement, and customer demand reinforces sustained use. The resulting ISM hierarchy provides a structured basis for policy and provider interventions, emphasizing targeted awareness initiatives, trust-building measures, simplified user journeys, reliable digital infrastructure, and vendor-centric support.

Keywords: Financial inclusion; mobile banking; street vendors; UTAUT; interpretive structural modeling; Pakistan; fintech adoption

Introduction

In the contemporary global economy, financial inclusion has emerged as a critical lever for socio-economic empowerment, poverty alleviation, and inclusive development. Institutions such as the World Bank and the United Nations (UN) have consistently underscored its importance in achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 1 (No Poverty), Goal 5 (Gender Equality), and Goal 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) (Le et al., 2019). Access to affordable, appropriate, and secure financial services not only enhances household resilience but also catalyzes entrepreneurship, supports savings and investment, and enables broader participation in formal economic activity. However, in many low- and

middle-income countries, large segments of the population—especially those working in the informal sector—remain financially excluded due to systemic, structural, and informational barriers.

Against this backdrop, the rapid growth of financial technology (FinTech) has redefined the contours of financial inclusion. FinTech innovations enable the design and delivery of financial services that are faster, more scalable, and more inclusive than conventional banking systems. Among these innovations, mobile banking—defined as the use of mobile phones to access a wide range of financial services including payments, transfers, savings, and credit—has emerged as a transformative channel. It enables users to conduct transactions without the need to visit a bank branch, thereby eliminating physical and procedural constraints that disproportionately affect marginalized populations.

The proliferation of mobile financial services is evidenced by global trends. As Arner et al. (2018) argue, the convergence of digital infrastructure with financial services is unlocking unprecedented access to finance in emerging markets. According to the 2025 GSMA Mobile Money Report, over 28 billion registered mobile money accounts exist globally, with 63 billion transactions conducted annually and a sustained growth rate exceeding 20%. Africa dominates global usage, accounting for approximately 70% of all mobile money transactions, while countries in South and Southeast Asia—such as Bangladesh, India, and Indonesia—exhibit strong upward trajectories. The expansion is driven by multiple enablers: increasing smartphone penetration (now over 5.3 billion users globally), robust agent networks, regulatory support for digital finance, and public-private partnerships between mobile network operators and financial institutions (Raithatha et al., 2023).

Pakistan reflects similar trends in digital financial transformation. The proliferation of mobile-based financial services such as EasyPaisa, JazzCash, and Upaisa has reshaped the country's financial landscape. Mobile banking has made inroads even in remote and underserved areas, owing to expanding mobile coverage, affordability of smartphones, and government-backed efforts to promote financial inclusion. The National Financial Inclusion Strategy (NFIS), the State Bank of Pakistan's branchless banking framework, and the more recent Banking on Equality initiative signal a clear policy commitment toward bridging the financial access gap (Noreen et al., 2022). Yet despite these advances, a large portion of the urban informal workforce remains disconnected from digital financial services. In particular, street hawkers and small vendors—who form a substantial part of Pakistan's urban economy—continue to face exclusion

due to a combination of technological, informational, and institutional constraints.

Street vendors typically operate outside formal economic and regulatory frameworks. Often without legal registration, bank accounts, or digital financial identities, they are vulnerable to financial shocks and lack access to formal credit, savings, or insurance mechanisms. In Pakistan, this group is highly heterogeneous and spans a wide range of micro-entrepreneurial activities, from food stalls and fruit carts to mobile phone accessories and household goods. These vendors are integral to urban life, offering low-cost goods to millions of consumers daily, yet they are routinely ignored in financial sector planning. Prior research (Dharejo et al., 2022) notes that these workers often lack awareness of digital financial tools, face literacy and trust barriers, and depend on informal cash transactions, which hinder business growth and economic mobility. While studies in regions like Sindh have documented some of these challenges, the specific behavioral, social, and infrastructural drivers of mobile banking adoption among urban vendors remain under-explored. This is particularly true for Islamabad, the federal capital, which provides a unique setting for examining fintech usage in an urban environment characterized by diverse socioeconomic strata, relatively stable digital infrastructure, and visible informal commerce clusters (e.g., G-6 Aabpara, F-10 Markaz, and Jinnah Super Market). Islamabad's market ecology allows for comparative insights across vendor types, and its status as a policy and financial hub offers relevance for potential scaling of inclusion strategies.

This study addresses a critical research gap by exploring the determinants and usage patterns of mobile banking adoption among street hawkers and vendors in Islamabad. Specifically, it investigates how technological, social, and economic factors interact to influence adoption behavior; how vendors perceive mobile financial services in terms of usability, trust, and value; and how their daily business practices are shaped by or resistant to digital finance. The research is anchored in the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), which has been widely validated in the study of technology acceptance across different user groups. The UTAUT framework identifies four core constructs—performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions—that together shape individuals' intentions and behaviors toward new technologies. These constructs are particularly well-suited to informal economic settings, where adoption is shaped by social norms, perceived benefits, and infrastructural limitations.

In addition, the study integrates Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) to identify and map the hierarchical interrelationships among the key factors influencing mobile banking adoption. While UTAUT offers a conceptual lens for understanding behavioral drivers, ISM allows for a structured, data-driven visualization of how different variables interact and reinforce each other. Together, these frameworks offer a robust methodological toolkit for analyzing the complex, multi-level dynamics of fintech adoption in informal sectors.

By centering the lived experiences and perceptions of street vendors, this research seeks to contribute both to academic discourse and to practical policy. It aims to inform targeted interventions—such as user-centered fintech design, awareness campaigns, and digital literacy initiatives—that are essential for advancing digital financial inclusion among Pakistan’s most economically vulnerable populations.

Literature Review

The discourse on financial inclusion has evolved significantly over recent decades, shaped by the convergence of socio-economic, technological, and institutional factors. While traditional financial systems have long struggled to serve low-income and informal populations, the rise of financial technology (FinTech) offers a transformative pathway toward inclusive finance. A review of existing literature reveals several key themes—drivers of financial inclusion, the intersection of FinTech with informal economies, adoption patterns among hawkers and street vendors, and the barriers that hinder broader access to digital finance.

Financial inclusion is a multidimensional concept, deeply influenced by economic development levels, demographic dynamics, infrastructure, and digital literacy. In the context of developed and transitioning economies, such as the European Union, financial inclusion is often driven by information and communication technology (ICT) penetration. As Bayar et al. (2021) note, mobile phone subscriptions and high internet usage are positively correlated with access to financial institutions and markets in post-communist European countries. Similarly, Le et al. (2019), examining 20 Asian countries, found that high economic growth, income levels, and literacy significantly enhance financial inclusion, while unemployment and rural residency hinder it. Ngo (2019) reinforces this by demonstrating how digital infrastructure, urbanization, and income levels directly impact the Index of Financial Inclusion (IFI) in Asia.

In South Asian contexts, the drivers of financial inclusion become more localized and layered. For example, Nandru et al. (2016) focus on South Indian states, highlighting that population density, balanced gender

ratios, and access to bank branches are critical enablers, while literacy showed an insignificant effect in some regions. In Pakistan, Razzaq et al. (2024) emphasize the gendered nature of financial exclusion, calling for gender-responsive financial policies. These findings underscore that financial inclusion is context-dependent and shaped by an interplay of social norms, infrastructure, and policy interventions. Sanderson et al. (2018) further emphasize the need for “lite” Know-Your-Customer (KYC) procedures to reduce documentation burdens in low-literacy contexts such as Zimbabwe. Similarly, Kaliba et al. (2023) observe that barriers like account maintenance costs prevent low-income Tanzanians from sustaining financial engagement even when accounts are initially opened.

FinTech has emerged as a key policy and research priority in developing countries where traditional banking often excludes vast portions of the population. Buckley and Webster (2016) argue that understanding the unique customer journey in such settings is essential for meaningful financial innovation. Arner et al. (2018) propose that effective digital financial inclusion requires integrated frameworks involving digital identification, mobile payments, and legal support systems. Haddad and Hornuf (2019), through a panel study of 64 countries, show that economic growth, mobile phone penetration, and internet access are significant determinants of FinTech development. In Pakistan, Ashraf et al. (2022a) apply the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), concluding that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions all influence fintech adoption.

Recent literature has also focused on environmental and ethical dimensions of financial inclusion. Nassiry (2018) explores how blockchain-enabled FinTech can support green finance, ensuring accountability and traceability of development funds. Baber (2020) provides a comparative study showing that financial inclusion tends to be higher in Islamic finance countries despite lower overall FinTech adoption, raising important questions about regulatory compatibility and the cultural adaptation of digital tools. A growing body of research has begun to focus on the intersection of FinTech and informal workers, particularly street hawkers and vendors. These individuals represent a crucial yet underserved segment of the urban informal economy. Donovan (2012) posits that mobile money holds potential for inclusion, but structural challenges persist. Bakhshi et al. (2024), using Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM), identify key barriers to FinTech adoption among Indian hawkers, including perceived risk, lack of awareness, low financial literacy, and trust deficits. These findings are echoed by Kunal et al. (2025), who show that FinTech

adoption among hawkers can lead to a 15% increase in daily sales, though variations exist based on age and education levels. Ahmad et al. (2021), employing the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), highlight that ease of use, perceived usefulness, and behavioral intentions are positively correlated with adoption. Rajkonwar (2024) further underscores the foundational role of financial literacy, noting that only 35% of street vendors in Assam possess the necessary financial capability, with demographic factors such as gender, education, and economic status influencing adoption.

Parallel to this, a broader literature on street vendors and hawkers situates them within the informal economy, often highlighting their vulnerability and exclusion from urban planning and financial systems. Recchi (2021) contrasts the regulated street vending of developed countries with the precarious conditions in developing regions, where vending is often a primary livelihood for the less educated. Peimani and Kamalipour (2022) argue that exclusionary urban policies, gender discrimination, and lack of access to public space limit vendors' ability to thrive. Bromley (2000) sees street vending as a persistent urban phenomenon that provides critical services to underserved markets while offering income opportunities to marginalized groups, despite frequent harassment and eviction. In Pakistan, Ahmed et al. (2021) and Dharejo et al. (2022) document the economic significance of hawkers and the structural challenges they face, particularly in accessing public spaces and formal financial services.

Despite global enthusiasm for digital financial inclusion, multiple barriers continue to constrain adoption, especially in developing and emerging economies. Simatele and Maciko (2022), examining rural South Africa, find that high banking fees and physical distance from financial institutions discourage active usage. Ediagbonya and Tioluwani (2023) report that in Nigeria, issues such as financial illiteracy, inadequate digital infrastructure, high service charges, and concerns over data privacy hinder fintech penetration. In Pakistan, Qaiser and Fahad (2024) highlight regulatory, security, and awareness challenges. Nizam and Rashidi (2024) delve into customer experiences with digital services and identify financial illiteracy, poor access to technology, and infrastructural deficiencies as key impediments to broader inclusion.

Policy responses to these barriers have varied in scope and effectiveness. In Pakistan, Akhtar (2003) notes that despite efforts by the State Bank of Pakistan, financial penetration remains low, with only 37% of adults owning bank accounts. Noreen et al. (2022) highlight promising gender-sensitive policies such as the Banking on Equality framework but

note the need for deeper implementation. Comparative insights from other countries are instructive: in the U.S., Figart (2013) attributes exclusion to institutional factors rather than financial illiteracy; in India and Nepal, studies by Sakariya (2013), Aggarwal & Klapper (2013), and Pant (2016) emphasize context-specific policymaking, expanded microfinance, and improved financial literacy. However, Sinha and Piedra (2021) caution that many financial inclusion initiatives prioritize short-term visibility over sustained impact due to weak outreach.

Some of the most effective models of digital financial inclusion have emerged from countries like Kenya and Bangladesh. Kenya's M-Pesa model is widely regarded as a global success story in mobile money, having revolutionized financial access through a user-centric design, robust agent network, and trust-based community integration. In Bangladesh, platforms such as bKash have achieved large-scale adoption through agent-supported transactions, minimal documentation, and integration with microfinance institutions. These models show that success hinges not just on technology, but on aligning design with users' capabilities and needs. The application of theoretical models such as UTAUT, TAM, and ISM is increasingly common in analyzing fintech adoption in these contexts. UTAUT has been especially influential for its ability to account for performance expectations, effort, social norms, and infrastructural support. TAM, while more narrowly focused on perceived usefulness and ease of use, has proven adaptable to low-literacy contexts when combined with behavioral frameworks. ISM, in contrast, is less common but valuable for mapping interdependencies among variables—particularly in settings like informal economies where multiple soft constraints interact to shape adoption behavior.

In summary, the literature suggests that while FinTech offers a promising vehicle for financial inclusion—especially through mobile banking—its success among informal workers like street vendors depends on context-sensitive strategies. These must account for low literacy, trust deficits, cost sensitivity, gender-specific constraints, and infrastructural limitations. There remains a significant gap in empirical studies exploring how street hawkers in cities like Islamabad experience, adapt to, or resist digital financial services. Addressing this gap through grounded research can inform both theory and practice in digital inclusion.

Methodology

Philosophical Foundations

Philosophical position of the researcher's guide assumptions about the world and influence all stages of the research process (Khan, 2023a). In social research, ontology refers to the nature of reality which involves

views about what exists and how it can be understood while epistemology deals with how knowledge is produced and how it can be interpreted (Scotland, 2012). In this study, ontological stance is constructivist which implies that reality is considered to be constructed subjectively based on social interactions, individual experiences and contextual influences. This aligns with the idea that technology adoption is not guided by universal laws rather it depends on and is shaped by socio-economic environment of users (Creswell & Poth, 2016). The study is based on interpretive epistemological position which holds that knowledge is subjective and is understood through the meaning that individuals assign to the phenomena in their surroundings rather than testing predefined hypotheses (Willis, 2007).

As the research aims to explore how street hawkers and vendors engage with mobile banking platforms, a constructivist ontological position combined with an interpretive epistemological stance enables a clear understanding of participants' lived experiences, contextual realities and socially constructed meanings associated with the use or non-use of mobile banking services. Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) was implied as theoretical foundation, which aligns with interpretivist epistemology. It guides exploration of how street hawkers and vendors in Islamabad perceive and adopt mobile banking platforms. Constructs such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions provide insights into subjective experiences of users.

Research Design

This research was based on an exploratory research design. The research aimed to understand how and why street hawkers and vendors utilize mobile banking services, a topic which is relatively under-researched in the context of the informal economy in Islamabad. This makes an exploratory research approach ideal. As street vendors primarily operate in an informal network, a qualitative exploratory research design allows for capturing social, technological, and economic aspects. (Stebbins, 2001) highlight that exploratory research helps develop insights rather than testing existing hypotheses. Moreover, this research design allows for data collection and interpretations, serving as a foundational step in unfolding mobile banking adoption behavior in the informal economy and contributing to broader discussion on financial inclusion in Pakistan.

Research Strategy

This Research was based on a Qualitative research strategy. Since this study seeks to explore various aspects of mobile banking adoption by street

hawkers and vendors in Islamabad, it required a strategy that allows for rich, descriptive, and contextually grounded insights. Qualitative research strategy is suitable for such research as it enables flexibility in data collection and analysis for a deeper understanding of social, economic and technological factors involved in the adaptation of mobile banking services (Creswell & Poth, 2016). According to (Khan et al., 2023b), Qualitative research is suited to exploring complex social phenomena, especially when the aim is to understand participants' subjective experiences, meanings and interactions in context. The strategy allows themes to emerge from data collected from end users / respondents rather than deriving themes from hypotheses, which supports exploratory research design. Furthermore, the strategy aligned well with the use of a theoretical framework based on Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) combined with interpretive structural modeling (ISM) which examined technology adoption patterns and structural relationships among influencing factors.

Theoretical Framework

This study seeks to investigate factors influencing mobile banking adoption among street hawkers and vendors in Islamabad. The theoretical foundation of this research is based on Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). This theory serves as guiding lens for understanding mobile banking (Technology) adoption patterns by street hawkers and vendors. To enhance the understanding of hierarchical relationships among influencing factors, the study integrates interpretive structural modelling as complementary method within theoretical framework.

Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) was proposed by (Venkatesh et al., 2003a). UTAUT is established on elements from eight prior technology acceptance models and is based on four constructs that influence technology adoption. These constructs include performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), social influence (SI) and facilitating conditions (FC). (Attuquayefio & Addo, 2014). These constructs are shown to be adaptable in diverse socio-economic environments such as in informal economies (Dwivedi et al., 2019).

Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM)

Interpretive structural modelling (ISM) is implied as an analytical method to systematically explore hierarchical relationships among variables involved in particular phenomena under consideration. ISM enables the formation of the structural model, which clearly identifies which factors are foundational (root cause) and which factors are more surface level (outcomes) (Warfield, 1974).

Application to Study Context

In the context of this study, Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology UTAUT is applied through constructs such as performance expectancy (PE) i.e., the degree to which hawkers believe that using mobile banking will improve their business performance, effort expectancy (EE) i.e., the perceived ease of usage and learning for mobile banking platforms, social influence (SI) i.e., the extent others influence hawkers' choice of mobile banking adoption and facilitating conditions (FC) i.e., availability of infrastructure, institutional and technical support. These constructs are crucial for understanding behavioural intentions influencing mobile banking adoption, However, the complex and multifaceted nature of such informal activities requires more than just identification of behavioural patterns involved in adoption of mobile banking technology. To address this complexity, Interpretive Structural Modelling (ISM) is integrated as a complementary approach to UTAUT. ISM will provide hierarchical illustration of various factors interlinked in the process of mobile banking adoption. This theoretical framework provides depth and structure to analyse how hawkers and street vendors engage with and perceive mobile banking adoption.

The above diagram is built around the Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) as central theoretical lens. The aim is to examine factors influencing adoption and use of mobile banking technology by street hawkers and vendors in Islamabad. Key constructs—performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions—are used to understand their behavioral intentions (perceptions) and actual use of mobile banking services.

Data Collection

Semi-Structured Interviews

The study implied semi-structured interview as primary method of data collection. Semi-structured interviews are a widely used qualitative data collection method combining flexible interview structure with guided questioning. The method allows the researcher to explore specific themes while getting detailed responses from participants (Kallio et al., 2016). These interviews provide deeper insights into participant responses, uncovering contextual drivers, social influences and technological challenges. These interviews maintain a balance between flexibility of open-ended conversations and consistency of a guided framework (Adams, 2015). For this study, Semi-structured interviews were essential for exploration of perceptions, experiences and usage patterns of mobile banking for street hawkers and vendors in Islamabad. This method aligned with the study's

interpretivist epistemological stance as it highlights participants' voices and supports meaning-making processes, Moreover, it complemented the exploratory design of the research, allowing themes to be identified organically through iterative dialogue. Interviews were conducted at their convenient places, mostly near their business areas and in their preferred language, mostly Urdu, Punjabi and Pashto. In order to ensure respondents' comfort and data authenticity, interviews were semi-structured so that clarification of responses could be made.

Transcription

Participants' consent was taken for audio recording before conducting the interviews. After that all the responses were transcribed and documented in the form of a Word document. The responses were transcribed in a way that conveyed the real meaning providing contextual annotations where required. Non-verbal cues and any interruptions like background activity were also recorded which added more depth to the conversations. Responses to each question in the interview guide were documented.

Coding and Thematic Development

After recording the transcriptions, a review of the transcripts was conducted in order to produce an initial codebook comprising of all themes identified by participants' responses and provided in UTAT and ISM framework.

Coding Procedure

I read each transcript several times for familiarization. Then I identified the parts of text that related to the research questions i.e., determinants of mobile banking adoption, perception of usefulness, usage patterns and societal influence. Codes were linked to meaningful phrases or sentences from participants' responses from the initial codebook. The major themes that I identified include usage patterns of mobile banking apps, perceived benefits, Literacy barriers, social influence and business impacts. All coding was performed in excel so that comparison could be made easy and data could be retrieved later. This ensured an in-depth and comprehensive thematic structure.

Sampling and Participant Profile

The study was based on purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling is widely used in qualitative studies to identify cases which can provide maximum and rich information on issue under consideration (Palinkas et al., 2015). Criteria-based purposive sampling technique was implied for selection of street hawkers and vendors from Islamabad who are either currently using mobile banking services (such as Easy Paisa, Jazz Cash, etc.) or are potential users of these services. In order to ensure diversity in

perspectives, the sampling considered variations in terms of age, gender, education and type of vending activity.

The research participants were males, aged between 20 - 60 years. Most of them had completed middle level of education with some having no formal education. Their linguistic background was also diverse, most of them could understand Urdu; their preferred languages were Punjabi and Pashto. Their business experience varied from 1-2 years to longer periods of almost 15-20 years. Most of them worked in partnership with family members, having fixed stalls, selling food items, household goods and jewellery. Some operated mobile stalls, selling fruits, vegetables, ice cream and other food items. Their average daily earnings ranged from 1000-3000 PKR.

The technological familiarity of the participants was also varied. Some of them could comfortably use smartphones for social media, calls or for financial banking apps while others had limited competency in using mobile technology. Most of the participants had not received any formal training for mobile banking apps for their businesses; they learned it either from their peers, customers or through observation. This diverse sample provided a rich context for analyzing the determinants of mobile banking in Islamabad's vibrant street economy.

Study Locale

The study was conducted in selected commercial zones across Islamabad that are known for high concentration of informal economic activity in Islamabad. These include Jinnah Super Market (F-7 Markaz), Super Market (F-6 Markaz), F-10 Markaz, Aabpara Market (G-6), G-11 Markaz and I-10 Markaz. These areas represent diverse urban clusters within Islamabad's metropolitan structure.

Data Analysis Procedures

Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM): Rationale and Application

Interpretive structural modeling (ISM) is a well-established qualitative analyses technique designed to analyze factors defining a particular issue or problem. Initially developed by John N. Warfield in 1973, the primary objective of ISM is to study complex issues as logical and understandable graphs (Warfield, 1974). The technique transforms poorly articulated models into clearly structured and hierarchical frameworks. According to Attri et al. (2013), ISM is defined as a process aimed at assisting the human being to better understand what he/she believes and to recognize clearly what he/she does not know.

ISM provides researchers with a systemic approach to impose direction and order to otherwise complex set of elements/factors. Based on expert

opinion and judgements, ISM allows generation of multilevel structure model for identification of independent (influencer) and dependent (influenced) factors. This identification leads to deeper understanding of issue as a whole (Warfield, 1978). Given the complex nature of mobile banking adoption by street hawkers and vendors in an urban area like Islamabad, ISM offers a practical approach for explanation of hierarchical influence of various determinants (socio-economic and technological). In this study, ISM was utilized for assessment of various elements contributing to mobile banking adoption by street hawkers and vendors in commercial as well as residential areas of Islamabad.

Why ISM in this Study?

Interpretive structural modeling (ISM) offers a context-sensitive approach to study the dynamics of complex issues (Ravi & Shankar, 2005). As major focus of this study was to explore structural relation among barriers and facilitators of mobile banking adoption, ISM technique provided in-depth exploration. The technique allowed identification and analysis of social, technical and institutional factors influencing mobile banking adoption by street hawkers and vendors in Islamabad. ISM accommodated expert opinions, judgements and contextual input making it adaptable to local realities where empirical data may be scarce. This is critical for policy makers who focus on addressing root cause of an existing problem rather than symptoms.

Application of ISM:

Interpretive structural modeling (ISM) has extensive application across various fields and disciplines which deal with complex and interrelated sets of variables. The flexibility and clarity of ISM enables researchers to identify and map key variables in complex environments (Attri et al., 2013). ISM has widespread application in fields such as supply chain management, environmental sustainability, policy planning, technology adoption and organizational strategy (Ebrahimi & Eynali, 2019). Practitioners imply ISM to identify dependent elements, deriving variables and to visualize the hierarchical structure among them. For example, in the domain of technology adoption, ISM helps in understanding how social, technological, and organizational factors interact to influence decision-making processes (Sage, 1977). Moreover, the method is useful in contexts where empirical data is limited but expert judgment is available, making it a suitable choice for exploring systems with qualitative complexity and unclear causal linkages.

Steps Involved in ISM:

1. **Identification of variables:** A comprehensive list of variables relevant to the issue under consideration is formulated based on literature review, expert opinions and contextual knowledge.
2. **Establishing Contextual Relationship:** A structural self-interaction matrix is developed to establish pairwise relationship among elements identified earlier.
3. **Developing Reachability Matrix:** The SSIM is converted into binary format to get a reachability matrix, which is checked for transitivity.
4. **Partitioning the Reachability Matrix:** The matrix is divided into reachability, antecedent and interaction sets. Hierarchical levels are defined.
5. **Constructing the ISM-Based Model:** A directed graph (diagraph) is created based on levels. The visual representation enables clear understanding of drivers and influencers.

Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis was used as primary method of data analysis for data collected through interviews. The process involved identification, analysis and interpretation of themes generated through recurring patterns in interview data. In-depth reading of transcripts was carried out in order to become familiar with data. The analysis provided detailed accounts of user perspectives and experiences related to mobile banking services. Codes were deducted inductively from the data. These themes include mobile banking adoption patterns, perceived benefits, social influence, challenges, business impacts and general attitude of users. After that, themes were verified and coherence was identified across and within interviews and data was modified where required. At the end, themes were refined to ensure alignment with research objectives and theoretical framework.

Findings and Analysis

Thematic Findings

The insights from in-depth interviews are presented through thematic analysis below.

Technological Engagement and User Experiences

Everyday experiences of street vendors with mobile banking reflects diverse patterns. Their engagement/ usage of mobile banking apps is shaped by multiple factors including direct encouragement from peers and customers, perceived value in terms of security and efficiency and benefits of digital access (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008). Responses suggest that, vendors mostly learned about mobile banking through social networks. Many respondents reported that their initial adoption of online payments (mobile banking) was

prompted by the influence of friends, *“My friend also uses mobile banking so, I have learned from him”* Another major aspect was ongoing customer demand *“Customers used to ask for online payments so I started using it”* This signifies the role of peer learning and market pressure for technology adoption.

The availability of up-to-date technology such as suitable devices and internet connectivity further enhances user experience and influences mobile banking adoption (Bhatt & Bhatt, 2016). The respondents with smartphones were able to explore a broader range of app features *“I use smart phone, can easily use EasyPaisa”* while, those with basic phones remained restricted in capability to experience mobile banking through apps *“I use simple feature phone for calls only”*. Vendor’s perceptions of ease of use and user-friendliness also play a decisive role in technology adoption, some describe mobile banking as *“Easy to use and makes my work fast”* whereas others struggle with literacy barriers stating that the app is complex *“I do not understand all app options but I work by recognizing signs on the app”*.

Other key factors shaping user experience are network reliability and transaction costs. Respondents mentioned these barriers as making their mobile banking experience difficult *“I face network issues, connectivity issues”* are frequently cited problems. Concerns about fees *“Shopkeeper charges me for sending money”* are also addressed by respondents. Moreover, trust on app reliability and safety of the app encourages mobile banking adoption reported as *“Yes, it keeps my money secure and I do trust mobile banking”* Thus a blend of factors including social influence, user perceptions and physical structure of mobile banking play crucial role in shaping user experiences of mobile banking adoption (Ashraf et al., 2022b).

Perceived Value and Business Impact

Mobile banking adoption patterns directly depend on user’s awareness and perceptions of possible improvements in business activities. According to most of the respondents, the perceived value of mobile banking adoption is rooted in its ability to provide convenience, efficiency and security in business transactions. Highlighting the tangible advantages of mobile banking for streamlining business activities, one vendor mentioned, *“Yes use of apps saves my time and money,”* while another respondent stated that *“It makes my work fast.”* Another aspect of vendor’s perceptions about mobile banking apps is money safety and security which emerged as a strong theme in interviews. As one of the respondent said *“It is helpful because money cannot be stolen from this app.”* Underscoring the peace of mind offered by digital cash handling relative to managing cash manually

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on busy streets, a respondent quoted, "It saves me from carrying too much cash" pointing to reduction in risk especially for vendors and hawkers working on busy streets. These responses highlight positive user perceptions for adoption of mobile banking services (Davis, 1989).

The business impact of mobile banking is reflected through changes individual workflow and customer demand relation and retention (Shareef et al., 2018). Specifically highlighting changes in the demographic profile of their clientele due to mobile banking adoption, a respondent said, "*More customers come on my stall due to online payments,*" and another stated, "*I do not lose customers as I give them facility of digital banking.*" A hawker at a busy area reported, "*Yes, more students come to my stall because I accept online payments*" The convenience of not needing to keeping "*extra change*" was quoted by a respondent as "*Now, I manage cash batter, less change is needed*" these responses suggest that digital payment options are contributing to smoother transactions and quicker service during busy periods.

Despite recognizing the value of mobile banking, multiple vendors repeatedly highlighted concerns about service charges and cash out costs. Multiple respondents shared, "*The shopkeeper charges me Rs 20 for 1000 cash withdrawal*" these extra costs eat into already tight margins, shaping usage patterns and even discouraging full adoption. The not using any mobile banking apps urged that "*There are hidden charges on transactions.*" Some vendors, despite using the digital payment apps, continue to prefer cash for most transactions because, as one respondent explained, "*I prefer cash over online payments,*" reflecting an attempt to avoid avoidable expenses.

Another interesting finding is that, not all users experience considerable improvements in business turnover. As one of the respondent shared, "*No my customers are the same as before, as students come to my shop mostly*" suggesting that for certain segments or locations, digital payments have not yet profoundly altered customer patterns or business volume, confirming the findings from developing countries (Aker & Mbiti, 2010). Several vendors mentioned that they only make limited use of mobile banking "*I use app for receiving payments from customers only*" but do not explore other functions like savings, bill payments or business loans. Indicating limited integration of mobile banking into wider business framework for street hawkers and vendors.

Social Dynamics and Influence

The adoption and sustained usage of mobile banking services for street vendors and hawkers is deeply rooted in their social context and relations

within their communities. Rather than relying of formal channels, Majority of vendors depend on informal/relational networks for guidance, support and confidence in adopting new technologies which is reflected through statements such as *“My son helps me using the app”* and *“I learned using the app from my friend”*

Majority vendors responded their first interaction with mobile banking platform was through practical demonstration and encouragement of fellow vendors. As one respondent described, *“I learned this from a shopkeeper next to my stall. He showed me step by step how to use the app to send and receive money. There was no training from the company, I just watched him and practiced with his help.”* Such responses emphasize the significance of trustworthy and accessible means of instruction as an alternative of formal training (Dholakia et al., 2004). Learning from friends also serves crucial role in shaping positive attitudes toward digital transactions *“My friends also use apps so I learned from them.”* The collective experience and endorsement from peers and fellows serve as a catalyst for building initial trust and lowering psychological barriers as vendors are more inclined to experiment with mobile banking when they see others in similar circumstances managing it successfully.

Furthermore, family dynamics help and reinforce the adoption of technology especially for those having limited or low literacy. Most of the vendors reported that they take assistance for technical matters from their younger or tech-friendly relatives: *“My son helped me understand the app,”* and *“My brother used it, then he told me to install the app.”* These intergenerational influences help in lessening the barriers related to literacy and language and build more confidence. Family members encourage sustained attention to and engagement with technology through active demonstration and guidance.

Another most emphasizing aspect for mobile banking adoption is expectations for online payments from customers. *“Younger customers usually demand digital payments”, “Customers mostly prefer online payments,”* and *“Customers used to ask for online payment so I started using it.”* The response of most of the participants indicates that they get encouraged and motivated for updating to mobile banking due to their customers’ requirement. As more vendors shift to mobile banking, it is becoming common and acceptance is growing throughout the marketplaces: *“Almost everyone uses it now customers, especially younger ones, prefer it if we accept payments through EasyPaisa or JazzCash.”* As vendors observe and learn from each other, they get familiarize according to their requirements (Ullah et al., 2022). This leads to continued cycle of adoption

of digital banking and a source where each new adoption becomes an enforcer for others to adopt soon.

Barriers and Challenges

There are various multifaceted and interlinked technical, personal and social factors that become the barriers to adoption and continuous practice of mobile banking among street hawkers and small vendors of Islamabad. The fundamental barriers for vendors in adoption of mobile banking are low literacy levels and limited technical knowledge (Bakhshi et al., 2024). Respondents often reported difficulty in navigating app features that require multiple processing or are presented in unfamiliar language. One vendor shared, *"I am uneducated so I face difficulty in understanding options on the app,"* while another reflected, *"Too many steps confuse me."* Even those who regularly use digital banking apps reported lack of confidence in utilizing all app features. These issues get multiplied for those who cannot read or write as they navigate through icons or colors or they have to rely on some support for their transactions. Moreover, the lack of any formal training for using apps intensifies the matter, most of the respondents reported that they learned operating apps from their friends or family members and have to depend on others for support.

The reliability and trust of users is also affected by continued app connectivity and network issues. Troubles such as internet connections, slow app loading and server errors lead to fear, apprehensions, anxiety and inconvenience. According to a respondent, *"Sometimes there are network issues, otherwise it's fine,"* while another explained, *"When network is slow I fear losing money."* Network issues are especially a problem for mobile vendors compared to those with fixed stalls which makes smooth network coverage difficult.

Vendors' concern related to trust and security appear as a significant barrier in both perceived and actual consideration. Some participants reported direct and indirect issues of missing balance, delayed payments and technical errors. As reported by one participant: *"Sometimes balance goes missing, I Don't trust fully."* This creates lack of confidence in apps. There are others who are highly influenced by stories of frauds, they have heard in their social circle: *"I heard fraud cases from my friends, so I will not use mobile banking."* This narrative whether experienced directly or indirectly create a situation full of fear and anxiety and lack of trust especially among older vendors who perceive that technology is not accessible for them.

Facilitating Conditions

Facilitating conditions include both reliable support structure and better enabling resources. These conditions when fulfilled become a source for sustained and continual use of mobile banking adoption (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Informal support system i.e., support provided by shopkeepers and peers play a significant role in bridging the gap of knowledge and technical awareness. As one of the respondents said: “I take help from agents or shopkeepers when I get stuck.” Family members especially younger ones are of great assistance in this regard. One participant reported: “My son and a customer suggested it. That’s why I tried.”

Respondents also mentioned technical barriers that limit their usability of digital banking facilities. This requires mobile banking companies to make changes in their apps to make it accessible for their potential users. Participants responses such as: *“operate without internet”* and *“make app easy for people who cannot read”* are a reflection of their concern for those who have low literacy level, or are facing network issues. These responses depict the notion that technological advances will reduce dependence on others. Most vendors reported that they did not receive any formal training on adoption of mobile banking. As participants said: *“No training at all.”* Many respondents highlighted the need for basic in-market training in their familiar language and accessible format. As responded: *“They should guide us in easy language; they should give us training on all options of the app.”* Lack of such institutionalized training not only creates a barrier for new people to adopt mobile banking but also risks the sustenance of the existing users. Respondents also demanded the requirement for engagement with small business owners and training them on digital banking for their businesses. As one vendor put it, *“They should visit markets and explain to people like us,”* and another noted, *“More training in markets would help. Also support in simple Urdu.”* These suggestions highlight a community based learning requirement.

Mapping Findings to UTAUT

The alignment between study’s empirical findings generated from in-depth interviews of street hawkers and vendors and constructs of Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of technology (UTAUT) provides a comprehensive theoretical lens for interpreting mobile banking adoption among street vendors. Analysis of the narratives of respondents reveals that each of the core UTAUT dimension namely performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions are reflected in lived experiences, motivation, adoption barriers and decision making patterns of users and non-users of mobile banking in this context.

Performance Expectancy

Performance expectancy, or the belief that mobile banking will enhance business scale and efficiency has emerged as central theme throughout the analysis of vendor's narratives. Respondents consistently cite tangible benefits such as quicker transactions, increased customer satisfaction and improved cash management. Comments like *"Yes, use of apps saves my time and money"* and *"It helps me secure my money, no chance of theft"* exhibit strong evidence that performance expectancy in terms of perceived usefulness is among the primary motivators for mobile banking adoption. Vendors note that accepting digital payments draws more customers especially students and young customers indicating that anticipated business gains are realized in daily practice.

Effort Expectancy

Effort expectancy is reflected through the perceived ease or difficulty of using mobile apps. It is integral to both adoption decision and sustained use or non-use of digital banking services. Vendors who find the mobile banking apps useful, describe them as *"very useful, easy to use, and makes my work fast"* reflecting higher level of satisfaction. However, for less informed vendors, usage of mobile banking is constrained by challenges including language barriers, lack of digital literacy and complex or unclear interface reflected through responses such as *"I do not understand all app options but I work by recognizing signs on the app."* Effort expectancy is influenced by a wide range of factors where ease of use is a strong adoption driver, while perceived complexity or fear of mistakes hinders adoption, particularly for older or less educated respondents.

Social Influence

The social context shaped by extent and role of social interactions is crucial to diffusion and normalization of mobile banking adoption. Analysis of respondent's narratives reinforces the role of peer encouragement and guidance from family as key Social influence manifests through persistent encouragement from peers, guidance from family and frequent request from customers. Most of the vendors credit their social network for entry into mobile banking as one of the respondent stated, *"My friends also use mobile banking, so I have learned from them."* Emphasizing the role of customer demand as a catalyst for digital payment acceptance, a respondent cited, *"Customers used to ask for online payment so I started using it."* Hence mutual reinforcement of peer and customer demand creates a powerful social momentum, lowering psychological barriers and prompting those reluctant or unsure to mobile banking. This collective

influence accelerates the integration of digital payments within street markets.

Facilitating Conditions

Facilitating conditions is marked by a range of supporting factors including access to supporting digital infrastructure, resources and informal or formal training. The study reveals that device ownership and reliable internet remain foundational facilitators in promotion of mobile banking adoption. findings from respondent's narratives explicitly reveal that practical support most often comes from family members, shopkeepers, or mobile banking agents as cited by the respondents, "I take help from agents or shopkeepers when stuck." One of the most crucial facilitating condition i.e., training opportunity remains missing from financial landscape as expressed by several respondents as a desire for "training in simple Urdu", "apps with more symbols," guidance in markets."

Hence Integrating Unified Theory of Acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) with the findings of the study enable a structured theory-driven explanation based on varied experiences of small vendors and street hawkers in Islamabad. Each UTAUT constructs was witnessed in the field. Vendors' decision to adopt or restrain from digital finance depends not only on perceptions of utility and perceived ease, but also on the socio-technical network and infrastructural realities. The UTAUT therefore not only helps explain the patterns observed but highlights actionable areas for intervention such as user education, simplifying interface and community based training.

ISM Structural Analysis:

Data Analysis

The analysis is performed using interpretive structural modeling (ISM), detailed analysis is presented as follows.

Step 1: Element Extraction

Following nine elements/factors are identified as determinants of mobile banking adaptation among street hawkers and vendors based on detailed analysis of recurring themes from the interviews.

Awareness (AW): Knowledge of mobile banking apps and their benefits.

Accessibility (AC): Availability of smartphones and internet connectivity.

Trust (TR): Confidence in the security and reliability of mobile banking apps

Ease of Use (EU): Perceived user-friendliness of apps, including language and interface simplicity.

Cost (CO): Transaction fees and financial burdens.

Social Influence (SI): Influence of peers, family, or customers.

Financial Literacy (FL): Understanding of financial concepts and app functionalities.

Network Reliability (NR): Dependability of internet and app performance.

Customer Demand (CD): Pressure from customers to accept digital payments.

Step 2: Structural Self-Interaction Matrix (SSIM)

The SSIM captures pairwise relationships between elements, where:

- V: Element i leads to Element j.
- A: Element j leads to Element i.
- X: Mutual influence.
- O: No relationship.

Table 1: Structural Self-Interaction Matrix (SSIM)

	AW	AC	TR	EU	CO	SI	FL	NR	CD
AW	-	V	V	V	O	A	V	O	A
AC		-	O	V	V	O	O	A	O
TR			-	V	O	X	V	O	X
EU				-	O	O	A	O	O
CO					-	O	O	O	O
SI						-	V	O	X
FL							-	O	O
NR								-	O
CD									-

Interpretation

The relationship among determinants of mobile banking adoption is explained below.

AW (Awareness) as the Row Factor

AW→AC (V): Greater awareness of online payments services leads vendors to explore and seek out access to mobile banking. The respondents who don't know about digital finance, they are less likely to access it.

AW→TR (V): Becoming aware tends to foster trust on digital payments. Moreover, hearing success stories, marketing, or positive talk enhances confidence among vendors.

AW→EU (V): Awareness campaigns often demystify apps, making them seem easier. Frequent exposure to mobile banking reduces hesitation.

AW→CO (O): Awareness does not directly lower transaction costs.

AW→SI (A): Vendor's level of awareness is shaped by social influence i.e., peers, fellow vendors, family and customers.

AW→FL (V): Awareness is often the entry point for learning key concepts i.e., financial literacy starts with simple awareness.

AW→NR (O): Awareness of mobile banking cannot fix poor networks or infrastructure issues

AW→CD (A): Customer demand drives awareness of mobile banking adoption.

AC (Accessibility) as the Row Factor

AC→TR (O): Having access does not impact the level trust on mobile banking apps.

AC→EU (V): Having access to good quality mobile device and connectivity, ensures that the app is more likely to be “easy” to use.

AC→CO (V): Access (having a smartphone and reliable Internet connection) can lower some transaction barriers/costs.

AC→SI (O): Access to mobile banking services does not drive peer or social influence.

AC→FL (O): Access without financial literacy is possible (and sometimes, a problem).

AC→NR (A): Network reliability is a precondition for accessibility.

AC→CD (O): Access doesn't create demand, but is necessary to serve it.

TR (Trust) as the Row Factor

TR→EU (V): If vendors trust mobile banking, they are less hesitant/reluctant, and thus perceive it as easier to use.

TR→CO (O): Trust does not influence platform fees hence isn't related to cost.

TR→SI (X): Trust and social influence reinforce each other: trustworthy social influence busts trust, trust, in turn, makes vendors more likely to follow peers.

TR→FL (V): Trust in digital finance fosters willingness to learn (to become financially literate about digital finance).

TR→NR (O): Trust doesn't impact or upgrade the network availability.

TR→CD (X): Trust in digital money grows as customer demand for digital payments increase, at the same time, as trust spreads, customer demand can increase further.

EU (Ease of Use) as the Row Factor

EU→CO (O): Ease does not reduce transaction costs.

EU→SI (O): Perceived ease does not drive social influence by itself.

EU→FL (A): Financial literacy (FL) makes the system easy to understand and hence increases ease of use

EU→NR (O): Ease doesn't fix the external network. Nor network availability ensures ease of use for users

EU→CD (O): Ease alone doesn't drive demand. Nor customer demand derive ease of use

CO (Cost) as the Row Factor

CO→SI (O): Transaction costs don't directly impact social influence.

CO→FL (O): Costliness doesn't affect financial literacy.

CO→NR (O): Fees don't change network reliability.

CO→CD (O): Transaction charges are not a demand driver.

SI (Social Influence) as the Row Factor

SI→FL (V): encouragement from peers, fellow vendors and family leads to increased learning. Financial literacy grows as friends help friends.

SI→NR (O): Social influence can't fix networks. Nor network availability influence social influence.

SI→CD (X): Social influence and customer demand boost each other (when customers ask, vendors influence peers, and vice versa).

FL (Financial Literacy) as the Row Factor

FL→NR (O): Literacy will not directly improve infrastructure nor network availability can impact financial literacy.

FL→CD (O): Financial literacy doesn't directly create customer demand.

NR (Network Reliability) as the Row Factor

NR→CD (O): Reliability of connectivity does not itself boost customer demand (but it is required to meet it).

CD (Customer Demand) as the Row Factor

No "V", "A", or "X": As a final node, demand is outcome rather than a driver toward the other factors in this SSIM.

Step 3: Reachability Matrix

At this stage, the SSIM is converted into an initial binary reachability matrix, then adjusted for transitivity to produce the final reachability matrix. The symbols are replaced by binary numbers (0,1) for further analysis. Numbers are assigned based on following a standard set of rules that interprets notations (V, A, O, X)

V (leads to): Row factor influence or enables column factor,

A (is led by): Column factor influences or enables row factor.

X (mutual): Both row and column element influence each other.

(none): No direct influence or effect.

Table 2: Initial Reachability Matrix

	AW	AC	TR	EU	CO	SI	FL	NR	CD
AW	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0
AC	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
TR	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1

EU	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
CO	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
SI	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1
FL	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
NR	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
CD	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1

Table 3: Final Reachability Matrix (with transitivity)

	AW	AC	TR	EU	CO	SI	FL	NR	CD
AW	1	1	1	1	1*	0	1	1*	0
AC	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
TR	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
EU	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
CO	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
SI	0	0	1	1*	0	1	1	0	1
FL	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
NR	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
CD	0	0	1	1*	0	1	1*	0	1

Note: Asterisks (*) indicate transitive relationships.

Driving and Dependence Power

The classification of driving and dependence power indicates meaningful insights into role of each factor in the system.

- Driving power counts how many elements a factor can reach or influence i.e., how much it shapes the system.
- Dependence power counts how many factors influence or reach a given factor i.e., how much it is influenced by other elements.

Table 4: Dependence Power and Driving Power

Element	Driving Power	Dependence Power
AW	7	2
AC	3	2
TR	5	4
EU	1	6
CO	1	3
SI	5	3
FL	2	5
NR	1	2
CD	5	3

Step 4: Level Partitioning

Elements are partitioned into hierarchical levels based on reachability and antecedent sets.

Table 5: Level Partitioning

Element	Level
AW	3
AC	2
TR	2
EU	1
CO	1
SI	2
FL	1
NR	1
CD	2

Step 5: ISM Model

The hierarchical model is structured as follows:

- Level 3 (Base): Awareness (AW)
- Level 2: Accessibility (AC), Trust (TR), Social Influence (SI), Customer Demand (CD)
- Level 1 (Top): Ease of Use (EU), Cost (CO), Financial Literacy (FL), Network Reliability (NR)

Figure 4. 1: ISM DIAGRAPH

Interpretation

Level 3 Awareness (AW) is the foundational driver, influencing Accessibility, Trust, Ease of use

Level 2 elements (AC, TR, SI, CD) act as intermediaries, driven by awareness and affecting outcomes like Ease of Use, Cost and Financial Literacy.

Level 1 elements (EU, CO, FL, NR) are outcomes, indicating successful fintech adoption depends on addressing lower-level drivers.

Step 6: MICMAC Analysis

Elements were classified based on driving and dependence power into four quadrants:

Autonomous: Network Reliability (NR)

Dependent: Ease of Use (EU), Cost (CO), Financial Literacy (FL)

Linkage: Trust (TR), Social Influence (SI), Customer Demand (CD)

Independent: Awareness (AW), Accessibility (AC)

Table 6: MICMAC Analysis

Quadrant	Elements
Autonomous	NR (1,2)
Dependent	EU(1,6), CO(1,3),FL (2,5)
Linkage	TR(5,4), SI(5,4),CD(5,4)
Independent	AW(9,1), AC(4,2)

Figure 1. MICMAC Scatter Plot

X-axis: Dependence Power

Y-axis: Driving Power

Points: AW (1,9), AC (2,4), TR (4,5), EU (6,1), CO (3,1), SI (4,5), FL (5,2), NR (2,1), CD (4,5)

Interpretation

The MICMAC analysis generates a systemic categorization of the determinants of mobile banking adoption among street vendors and hawkers by evaluating each factor’s deriving and dependence power.

The analysis reveals that, the strongest independent drivers of mobile banking adoption are, **Awareness (AW) and Accessibility (AC)**: These elements possess significant influence over the entire adoption framework and are foundational for all subsequent determinants, yet they are themselves minimally influenced by other factors. Linking variables are

categorized as **Trust (TR)**, **Social Influence (SI)**, and **Customer Demand (CD)** as they both influence and are influenced by several other factors making them critical for systemic change but also sensitive to disruptions elsewhere in the digital ecosystem. **Ease of Use (EU)**, **Cost (CO)**, and **Financial Literacy (FL)** emerge as dependent variables, meaning they mainly reflect the outcomes of interventions elsewhere in the system rather than acting as root causes. Finally, **Network Reliability (NR)** is the only autonomous element, given its low driving and dependence power, indicating its role is more infrastructural and external to the behavioral or social determinants within the vendor community.

Overall, MICMAC analysis indicates that interventions focused on improving awareness and accessibility are likely to have most crucial impact, while strengthening linkages such as trust and social influence can magnify and sustain adoption across the vendor community.

Hierarchy and Interrelationships

ISM factors are classified based on their role in system. The factors are classified as key root causes (drivers), intermediaries or linkages and outcomes that emerge from the functioning of driving and intermediary factors.

Driving Factors

Awareness (AW) serves as the foremost driving factor for mobile banking adoption among street vendors. It represents vendors' knowledge of mobile banking services and their potential benefits. Raising awareness of digital technologies is starting point, as without it, further progress towards mobile banking adoption is impossible. Awareness stimulates curiosity and encourages learning about technology. Another important driving factor is Social Influence (SI), as encouragement and observable behaviors among peers or customer demands can prompt initial interest and willingness to try digital payments. Together, awareness and social influence are identified as foundational determinants, catalyzing the journey of adoption by making vendors receptive to new fintech possibilities.

Linking Factors

The model identifies four major linking factors including Accessibility (AC), Trust (TR), Customer Demand (CD) and Social Influence (SI). Accessibility refers to practical access to required technology (like smartphones and internet), which is primarily driven by awareness but also relies on infrastructural support through network reliability. Another critical factor is Trust (TR) which is built through positive experiences and effective app performance. Social influence serves as critical enablers that provides a linkage between foundational awareness and tangible outcomes. All these

factors together set enabling environment for mobile banking adoption. Trust reduces hesitation and fosters continued digital engagement. Social influence provides linkage, between basic awareness and meaningful use. Vendors who get guidance or awareness from peers and family understand the features and use digital tools are more likely to confidently operate bank apps and benefit from them. These linking factors ensure that initial awareness is converted into digital banking adoption and sustained usage patterns. Customer demand is both an outcome and a reinforcing factor as customers increasingly expect digital payment options, they drive vendors to adopt mobile banking channels.

Outcomes

The outcomes or dependent determinants of the adoption process are reflected in factors like Ease of Use (EU), Cost (CO), Network Reliability (NR), and Financial Literacy (FL)). Ease of use indicates how user-friendly the application feels to the vendor. It is largely dependent on driving and linking factors such as prior financial literacy, trust and quality of the interface. Cost in this context refers to transaction fees and is a key barrier that can limit mobile banking adoption and use pattern. Another determinant is network reliability. it is autonomous in the model but it determines the smooth functioning of fintech services. Persistent connectivity issues can vendor motivation to use digital channels.

Conclusion

This study explored the adoption of mobile banking among street hawkers and small vendors in Islamabad, identifying a complex interplay of social, economic, and technological factors. Awareness and social influence emerged as foundational enablers. Vendors typically gain knowledge about mobile banking platforms such as EasyPaisa, JazzCash, and SadaPay through informal peer networks, family members, and customers, rather than formal channels. This form of social diffusion aligns with the UTAUT construct of social influence, where community-based trust acts as a critical adoption motivator.

Economic considerations, particularly transaction costs, cash-out charges, and opportunity costs associated with service failure, serve as significant barriers to initial and sustained adoption. From a technological standpoint, accessibility through smartphone ownership and reliable network infrastructure is essential for functional use, while outages and device limitations hinder engagement.

Usage patterns among vendors indicate a strong preference for basic mobile banking functionalities, particularly payments and transfers. More advanced services like digital credit and micro-investments remain

underutilized, reflecting a broader pattern of limited digital literacy, risk aversion, and institutional distrust. Facilitating conditions such as smartphone availability and network reliability play a pivotal role in shaping frequency and type of usage.

Perceptions of mobile banking among vendors further reinforce UTAUT constructs. Vendors often cite the usefulness of mobile banking in simplifying transactions, improving customer service, and providing a safer alternative to cash handling. However, ease of use is perceived unevenly—those with higher digital and financial literacy engage more confidently, while those unfamiliar with mobile technologies report difficulties navigating app interfaces and understanding technical terminology. Trust in the safety and authenticity of digital platforms is another determining factor, strongly influencing adoption decisions.

Applying the UTAUT framework, the study confirms that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions are all salient in shaping adoption behaviors. These constructs are further contextualized through Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM), which reveals a hierarchical structure among adoption drivers. Awareness sits at the base of the ISM model, acting as a root trigger for all subsequent behaviors. At the intermediary level, accessibility and trust form critical bridges between intention and actual use. Outcome-level factors such as cost, usability, and network reliability directly influence long-term engagement and satisfaction. The ISM hierarchy highlights the need for multi-tiered interventions: foundational awareness must be cultivated, infrastructure and user trust must be strengthened, and advanced functionalities must be introduced with support mechanisms to promote deeper engagement. Without addressing these upstream constraints, downstream behaviors such as usage frequency and transaction variety will remain limited.

Customer demand appears both as a driver and a reinforcing consequence, suggesting a feedback loop in which vendor adoption of mobile payments promotes greater demand for digital transactions. However, significant barriers persist, particularly for vendors with limited education, older age, or unfamiliarity with mobile technology. These include perceived app complexity, network instability, and transaction costs—factors that discourage adoption and lead to cautious, limited use of mobile banking. The adoption of mobile banking by street vendors in Islamabad is shaped by a multifaceted matrix of influences—social, economic, technological, and perceptual—organized into a clearly tiered structure. The findings validate both UTAUT and ISM as appropriate analytical tools for understanding adoption in informal economies, while

offering empirical insights into vendor behavior in Pakistan's urban financial landscape

Limitations

The study had a few notable limitations. The sample was geographically restricted to urban areas of Islamabad, which limits the generalizability of findings to rural areas of the city. In addition, language and literacy limitations of participants posed challenges in fully capturing lived experiences, even though efforts were made to conduct interviews in local languages. Lastly, gender-specific barriers and enablers were not explored, presenting an important area for future research.

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Appendix

Level partitioning iteration tables are provided for transparency and replication.

Table A1. Level Partitioning Iteration 1

Table A2. Level Partitioning Iteration 2

Table A3. Level Partitioning Iteration 3

Iteration 3 (after removing AC, TR, SI, CD):				
Element	Reachability Set	Antecedent Set	Intersection	Level
AW	AW	AW, SI, CD	AW	3
Levels Assigned: AW (Level 3).				
Iteration 2 (after removing EU, CO, FL, NR):				
Element	Reachability Set	Antecedent Set	Intersection	Level
AW	AW, AC, TR	AW, SI, CD	AW	
AC	AC	AW, AC	AC	2
TR	TR, SI, CD	AW, TR, SI, CD	TR, SI, CD	2
SI	TR, SI, CD	AW, TR, SI, CD	TR, SI, CD	2
CD	TR, SI, CD	AW, TR, SI, CD	TR, SI, CD	2

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Levels Assigned: AC, TR, SI, CD (Level 2).				
Iteration 1:				
Element	Reachability Set	Antecedent Set	Intersection	Level
AW	AW,AC,TR,EU,CO, I,FL,NR,	AW, SI, CD	AW	
AC	AC,EU,CO	AW,AC, NR	AC	
TR	TR,EU,SI,FL,CD	AW,TR,SI,CD	TR,SI,CD	
EU	EU	AW,AC,TR,EU,SI,FL,CD	EU	1
CO	CO	AW,AC,CO	CO	1
SI	TR,EU,SI,FL,CD	AW,TR,SI,CD	TR,SI,CD	
FL	EU,FL	AW,TR,SI,FL,CD	FL	1
NR	NR	AW,AC,NR	NR	1
CD	TR,EU,SI,FL,CD	AW,TR,SI,CD	TR,SI,CD	
Levels Assigned: EU, CO, FL, NR (Level 1).				